

A SOCIOLOGICAL STUDY OF SOCIAL COMPETENCE AND EMOTIONAL MATURITY AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The study was investigated a sociological study of social competence and emotional maturity among university students. Objectives were to find out the level of emotional maturity and social competence and to find out the significant relationship of emotional maturity with social competence among university students. 200 students were selected using random sampling technique from Chandigarh University Tools on social competence by Sharma and Sharma (2010) and emotional maturity by Sharma, Shukla, and Shukla (2012) were used to collect the data. The findings of the study revealed that no significance difference in both social competence and emotional maturity of boys and girls. Significant relationship was found between social competence and emotional maturity. The more a person has control over his emotions; higher are the chances to be socially competent. It is suggested to teachers and parents that proper environment should be provided in the university and family for the development emotional maturity.

Key words:- Social Competence, Emotional Maturity

INTRODUCTION

Emotions are essential in our lives. They come to us effortlessly, like inhaling air. They serve as a vital means of interaction between a person and their surroundings; we convey our emotions and ideas by showing a range of feelings. The term "emotion" refers to feelings like fear, happiness, rage, affection, envy, and unease. Expressing feelings is a crucial aspect of our existence and provides insight into how various things impact us. Humans are beings full of emotions, and our initial reaction to a stimulus is emotional. Emotions can exert a powerful influence over us, and under the sway of passion, we frequently overpower reason. They are the urges to act, at times illogically, that evolution has provided us (Scaruffi, 2006). Adolescence is a time of swift social development as students begin to recognize themselves through social interactions. Emotions are crucial in social skills and greatly affect individuals' thoughts, perceptions, and behaviors. Social competence involves the capacity to participate in significant interactions with others that contribute to the development of adolescents' maturity levels.

DEFINITIONS

Social Competence: - Social competence refers to a child's effectiveness in participating in social interactions with peers and adults (Fabes et al. 2006)

Emotional Maturity: - Emotional maturity can be defined as a process in which personality is always determined by a greater sense of emotional well-being (Manninger, 2015).

Review of Related Literature

Studies related to Social Competence and Emotional Maturity

Gupta and Gupta (2013) examined how Perceived Emotional Intelligence and social competences impact academic performance. A total of one hundred ninety-three students (50.7% male and 49.3%

female) from the first and second cycle of secondary school ("M" = 14.1 years; "DT" = 1.39; aged between 11 and 16 years) participated in a self-report assessing Perceived Emotional Intelligence (TMMS-24) and Social Attitudes (AECS). Academic performance was evaluated through individual grades and a customized Likert scale that included various behavior indicators measuring teachers' expectations regarding performance. Findings indicated that prosocial attitudes had a positive and significant predictive effect on both students' academic performance and Perceived Emotional Intelligence.

Wendys, Knobe, and Carolien (2017) investigated if a specific type of social play enhances the growth of social competence, or if simply having the chance to interact during recess offers children a favorable setting for social learning. Seventy-three preschoolers (ages 4 to 6) were recorded on video at the school playground. Educators assessed children's social skills. Less crowded peer groups and extended interactions showed a beneficial relationship with the social competence of these preschoolers. The research highlighted the significance of outdoor active play for preschoolers' social achievement.

Collie (2020) built upon the earlier conceptualization by introducing a model of social and emotional competence that acknowledges both the processes and the expressions of social and emotional competence. The actions subsequently foster the fulfillment of needs in an ongoing loop. The associations discovered through the iterative process are impacted by the necessity for support in the social context, and these associations both affect and are affected by personal differences and human development.

Kumar and Rawat (2024) discovered the connection between the social and emotional development of secondary school students. They must grow adequately to sustain our community and to achieve a more fulfilling and prosperous existence for themselves. The findings also showed that female students are notably more socially developed than male students. The emotional maturity levels of male and female students differ greatly.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The literature review indicates that no clear conclusion can be reached about the importance of differences in social competence between boys and girls, nor about the significance of differences in their emotional maturity. There has been a lack of research, with very few studies conducted, on the connection between the social competence and emotional maturity of university students. The investigator discovered studies by Wendys, Knobe, and Carolien (2017) along with Collie (2020), which indicated a distinction between social competence and emotional maturity. Research by Moana (2015) and Kumar and Rawat (2024) explored the link between emotional maturity and social competence. The proposed study appears fully warranted, as no clear conclusion can be reached regarding the connection between social competence and emotional maturity; therefore, the researcher aims to determine whether a relationship exists between these constructs among university students.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To find out the level of emotional maturity and social competence of among university students.
- 2) To find out the significant relationship of emotional maturity with social competence among university students

Hypotheses of the Study

- 1) There will be no significant difference between emotional maturity and social competence among university students.

2) There will be no significant relationship of emotional maturity with social competence among university students.

Design of the study

To investigate a sociological study of Social Competence and Emotional Maturity among university, a descriptive study has been designed in which survey method was adopted.

Sample of the study

A sample of 200 students of Chandigarh University was taken for the present study. There were 100 boys and 100 girls in sample of 200 students. The data was collected by random sampling technique.

Tools used for data collection

The researcher used the tools, questionnaire on social competence by Sharma and Sharma (2010) and emotional maturity by Sharma, Shukla, and Shukla (2012).

Analysis and interpretation of data

Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, Pearson coefficient of correlation and t-ratio were calculated by using SPSS.

Discussion of result and findings are as follows.

The descriptive statistics of scores obtained by boys and girls on emotional maturity and social competence of University students were computed.

Table 4.1 Level of emotional maturity and social competence in boys and girls

Variables	Boys		95% CI	
	Mean	SD	Upper	Lower
Emotional Maturity	207.4	18.0	207.4	194.1
Social Competence	144.2	15.8	150.0	138.4

Variables	Girls		95% CI	
	Mean	SD	Upper	Lower
Emotional Maturity	197.0	23.2	205.1	188.8
Social Competence	136.8	15.9	145.1	133.8

Table 4.1 shows the participants' levels of emotional maturity and social competence. For boys, the mean emotional maturity score was 207.4 (upper limit 207.4, lower limit 194.1). The mean social competence score was 144.2 (upper limit 150.0, lower limit 138.4). For girls, the mean emotional maturity score was 197.0 (upper limit 205.1, lower limit 188.8). The mean social competence score was 136.8 (upper limit 145.1, lower limit 133.8).

Table 4.2. Relationship of emotional maturity with social competence of boys and girls

Variables	r value
Emotional Maturity and Social Competence of Boys	.487*
Emotional Maturity and Social Competence of Girls	.370*

* Significant at 0.01 level of significance

Table 4.2 shows the relationship between emotional maturity and social competence in boys and girls. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to calculate this relationship. In boys, a statistically significant ($p < 0.01$) positive relationship was observed between emotional maturity and social competence ($r = 0.487$), indicating that greater emotional maturity is associated with greater social competence. In girls, a statistically significant ($p < 0.01$) positive relationship was also found between emotional maturity and social competence ($r = 0.370$), indicating that greater emotional maturity is associated with greater social competence. This demonstrates a statistically significant relationship between emotional maturity and social competence.

Finding and Conclusion of the study

Analysis of the data collected from the relevant study sample suggests a significant relationship between emotional maturity and social competence among university students. It was concluded that levels of emotional maturity influence adolescents' social competence. The greater a person's emotional control, the greater their likelihood of being socially competent. In this sense, the present study found an interdependent relationship between emotional maturity and social competence.

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